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Influence of Family Instability on Psychological Adjustments of Secondary School Students in Konshisha Local Government Area, Benue State

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of family instability on psychological adjustment of secondary school students in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State. Descriptive research design was employed for the study. The population was 7,592 secondary school students. A sample of two hundred and fourteen (214) respondents was used. The study employed simple random sampling technique. Four-point rating scale was used as instrument for data collection. Four research questions guided the study four researcher hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions and Chi-square test of goodness of fit to test hypotheses. The study revealed among others that; Family instability has significant influence on self-actualization, self-concept, self-esteem and self-efficacy of secondary school students in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State. The study recommended among other things that; Parents should seek counselling as a professional way of resolving conflicts rather than aggressive means which will affect their children's psychological well-being. Also, that Parents should always provide the warmth environment their children need in order to develop a balanced self-concept, a good self-image for them to self-actualize their goals.

Keywords: Family Instability, Psychological Adjustment, Self-actualization, Self-concept.

INTRODUCTION

Family instability refers to the frequent and/or significant changes in the structure and dynamics of a family, which can include changes in family composition, parenting arrangements, residence, and relationships. Family instability can manifest in various forms, such as parental separation or divorce, remarriage or cohabitation, frequent moves, changes in household composition (for instance, new partners or step-siblings), and disruptions in parenting arrangements (for instance, custody battles). It refers to changes in parents' residential and romantic partnerships, such as marriage, divorce, and romantic partners moving in or out of the home (Amato 2017). Family instability has become a problem many families everywhere around the world, in the region and also in the communities. When separation happens in a family it affects both parents and children, but mostly children take a big percentage of suffering the consequences (Heard, 2017). It is expected that 75 percent of African children born to married parents will

experience their parents' conflict before the age of sixteen (Amato and Keith, 2011). The role that parents play in the upbringing of a child is very important. Children look up-to their parents for guidance, protection and motivation to live a great life. However, family instability affects these needs. The dramatic changes in the physical appearance of young people triggered by pubertal development can lead individuals to treat students differently; expecting more adult, and often more gender typical, behaviour from them (Bumpus, Crouter, & McHale, 2011). Adjustment of adolescents to all the changes identified by the above scholars is necessary for psychological stability of study.

Psychological adjustment depends upon satisfactory insight into the events and psychological changes that have occurred and a personal acceptance of these changes; an appropriate adjustment of the perception of self; a modification of beliefs and personal goals; and the acquisition of appropriate strategies to compensate for any residual handicap. It implies not only psychological adjustment, but also the re-establishment of personal, family and social relationships, both intimate and more distant. It may also involve occupational adjustment and redefinition of personal roles in all these contexts. This psychologist must understand and have the skills to facilitate. According to Horney (2020) people adjustment can be classified in terms of three types of responses: people tend to deal with problems by either moving towards, away from them, or against them. Adjustment is negatively related with low self-esteem. Friedlander, Reid, Shupank, and Cribbie (2019) also stated that adjustment in university is enhanced by low stress and high level of self-esteem. Psychological adjustment is a function of self-actualization, psychosocial balance or development, self-esteem, ability to cop, develop a good self-concept. Self-actualization is the complete realization of one's potential, and the full development of one's abilities and appreciation for life. Based on humanistic psychology perspective, the concept of self-actualization and reaching full potential has brought us closer to understanding the complex psychological construct of an individual (Parker 2019). Self-actualization, self-realization and spiritual growth and development represent the optimal psychological stages for all individuals. As individuals grow and develop into whole and complete, self-actualized people, they seek to find more meaning in their life through the work. The result could be that the workplace may cease to be separate from the personal development space and transcending into a platform for individual growth (Konz and Ryan, in Parker 2019).

Self-esteem refers to individual's perception or subjective appraisal, of one's own self-worth, one's feelings of self-respect and self-confidence and. the extent to which the individual holds positive or negative views about self. The construct of self-esteem has a long and checked history within the discipline of psychology. William James in Marsh (2018), one of the first psychologists, first proposed that people develop high self-regard when they consistently meet their personally important goals or standards in life. Self-concept is an idea of the self-constructed from the beliefs one holds about oneself and the responses of others. The self-concept is a general term used to refer to how someone thinks about, evaluates or perceives themselves. Self-concept is our personal knowledge of who we are, encompassing all of our thoughts and feelings about ourselves physically, personally, and socially. Self-concept also includes our knowledge of how we behave, our capabilities, and our individual characteristics. Our self-concept develops most rapidly during early childhood and students, but self-concept continues to form and change over time as we learn more about ourselves. It refers to one's description and evaluation of oneself, including psychological and physical characteristics, qualities, skills, roles and so forth. Self-concepts contribute to the individual's sense of identity over time. The conscious representation of self-concept is dependent in part on no conscious schematization of the self (see schema). Although self-concepts are usually available to some degree to the consciousness, they may be inhibited from representation yet still influence judgment, mood, and behavioural patterns. Also called self-appraisal; self-assessment; self-evaluation; self-rating (Justus 2018). Looking at the observed consequences of family instability on children especially in-school, this study therefore intend to investigate the influence of family instability on psychological adjustment of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area of Benue State.

Statement of Problem

It has been observed that children from conflict prone families in Konshisha more often engage in delinquent acts than children from other homes where both parents are living together. There has been growing concern, by education stakeholders over the rate of family instability in Konshisha local government. It has been observed that; secondary school students in Konshisha local government experience a range of emotional problems, such as anxiety, depression, and stress, in response to family instability. Students are noticed to feel confused, angry, and sad about the changes happening in their family, and they struggle to express these emotions in a healthy way. Students who experience family instability may not psychologically, stable as to concentrate or not able to be focused enough to actualize academic targets such students may develop low self-concept, self-esteem and self-efficacy in school, which can lead to poor academic performance. They have trouble forming and maintaining relationships with peers, as well as with adults. They may feel isolated and withdrawn, or they may act out in an attempt to get attention. It is against this background that this study therefore seek to investigate the influence of family instability on psychological adjustments of secondary school students in Konshisha Local Government Area, Benue state.

Purpose of the Study

The main aim of the study was to investigate the influence of family instability on psychological adjustment of secondary school students in Konshisha local government Area, Benue State. Specially, the study sought to:

1. examine the influence of family instability on self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue state.
2. find out the influence of family instability on self-concept of secondary school students
3. determine the influence of family instability on self-esteem of secondary school students.

Research Questions

To achieve the purpose of the study, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. what is the influence of family instability self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue state?
2. to what extend does family instability influence self-concept of secondary school students?
3. how does family instability influence on self-esteem of secondary school students?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. family instability has no significant influence on self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State.
2. family instability has no significant influence on self-concept of secondary school students.
3. family instability has no significant influence on self-esteem of secondary school students.

RESEARCH METHOD

The researcher intend to adapt a descriptive research design, the reason for the choice of the descriptive research method is to ensure detailed systematic description of facts and characteristics of data to be collected for the study to help proper analysis and evaluation of findings. A descriptive research design is a way of organizing data and looking at the object to be studied as a whole. Descriptive Research design determines and describes the way things are. It seeks to describe a unit in detail, in context and holistically (Emaikwu, 2011). The research seeks to investigate the influence of family instability on psychological adjustment of students in Konshisha. The target population for this study comprised all 7,592 (seven thousand five hundred and ninety two). Students in the 48 secondary schools within the 12 council wards in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State (Source: Ministry of Education, Statistics Section Konshisha, 2023). The sample of the study was 214 respondents from 48 selected public secondary schools in Konshisha, representing the total population of 7,592. Simple random sampling technique is adopted for this study. In the process of randomization, hat and draw method is used where every student is given a number after which it is squeezed and raffled in a container. The researcher

picked the sampled number randomly without replacement, this is because it give every students equal opportunity to be selected without bias. The instrument for this research was a structured rating scale titled 'Family Instability and Students' Psychological Adjustment Rating Scale (FISPARS)". Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and chi-square was used to test the hypotheses of goodness of fit.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of family instability on self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue state?*

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation for family instability and self-actualization of secondary school students

Item	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6. The conflict going on in my family is gradually affecting my ambitions in life	214	3.15	.969	Accepted
7. I performance low among my class mate because my parents will rather quarrel than assist me with homework.	214	3.19	.957	Accepted
8. The conflict between my parents has made then to neglect my need to achieve the type of career I wanted for myself.	214	2.56	1.25	Accepted
9. I do not have enough time to study because my parents are always change environment, due to family disagreement.	214	3.08	1.10	Accepted
10. The conflict in my family is causing me to give up on my aspirations. The conflict in my family is causing me to give up on my aspirations.	214	2.88	.930	Accepted
Cluster Mean/SD		2.97	1.00	Accepted

Field Work, 2024

This Table indicates the mean ratings and standard deviation of respondents from items 1 to 5 as 3.15, 3.19, 2.56, 3.08, and 2.88, with their corresponding standard deviations of .969, .957, 1.25, 1.10, and .930, respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point with a cluster mean and standard deviation of **2.97** and **1.00**. This implies that family instability have significant influence on self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government Area of Benue State.

Research Question 2: *To what extend does family instability influence on self-concept of secondary school students?*

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation for family instability and self-concept of secondary school students

Item	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1. I feel unlucky to be born in my family because of constant conflict.	214	3.23	.894	Accepted
2. I wish I was born in a family with absolute harmony.	214	3.07	1.044	Accepted
3. I feel neglected living in a family with constant conflicts.	214	2.87	1.067	Accepted
4. I feel worthless each time there is conflict in my family.	214	2.97	1.102	Accepted
5. I feel homeless because of the constant conflicts in my family.	214	2.93	1.055	Accepted
Cluster Mean/SD		3.014	1.01	Accepted

Field Work, 2024

Table 2 revealed the mean ratings and standard deviation of respondents as 3.23, 3.07, 2.87, 2.97, and 2.93, with corresponding standard deviations of .894, 1.044, 1.067, 1.102, and 1.055, respectively. Respondents rated all the items above the 2.50 cut-off point with a total mean and standard deviation of **3.014** and **1.01**. This indicates that family instability have significant influence on self-concept of secondary school students in Konshisha local government Area of Benue State.

Research Question 3: *How does family instability influence on self-esteem of secondary school students?*

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation for family instability and self-esteem of secondary school students

Item	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1. I believe I can never be happy because my family is never in peace.	214	2.86	1.166	Accepted
2. I feel empty because I can't enjoy peace in my family.	214	2.75	1.147	Accepted
3. I don't think I am special like my friends who enjoy absolute harmony in their families.	214	3.28	1.055	Accepted
4. I don't see myself achieving anything good when there is always disunity in my family	214	2.36	1.047	Accepted
5. I feel depressed due to the constant disputes in my family.	214	3.33	1.001	Accepted
Cluster Mean/SD		2.91	1.03	Accepted

Field Work, 2024

Table 3 indicates the mean scores and standard deviation of respondents as 2.86, 2.75, 3.28, 2.36, and 3.33, with corresponding standard deviations of 1.166, 1.147, 1.055, 1.047, and 1.001, respectively. All the items were rated above the 2.50 cut-off point with a cluster mean and standard deviation of **2.91** and **1.03**. This implies that family instability have significant influence on self-esteem of secondary school students in Konshisha local government Area of Benue State.

Hypothesis 1: Family instability has no significant influence on self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State.

Table 4: *Chi-Square Test for the influence of family instability on self-actualization of secondary school in Konshisha local government area, Benue State*

Reponses Mode	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	Df	Level Sign	Chi-Square	P.value	Decision
VHE	453	53.5	3	0.05	274.97	0.00	Sig.
HE	282	53.5					
LE	188	53.5					
VLE	147	53.5					

Field Work, 2024

This table shows the chi-square values of 274.97, with observed frequency of responses as VHE453, HE288, LE188 and VLE147 under the difference of 3 with Chi-square value of 274.97 and P. value of .000. Since this value is less than the alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis which states that Family instability has no significant influence on self-actualization of secondary school students has been rejected. This implies that family instability have significant influence on self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State.

Hypothesis 2: Family instability has no significant influence on self-concept of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State.

Table 5: Chi-Square Test for the influence of family instability on self-concept of secondary school students

Reponses Mode	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	Df	Level Sign	Chi-Square	P.value	Decision
VHE	450	53.5	3	0.05	367.776	0.00	Sig.
HE	323	53.5					
LE	160	53.5					
VLE	137	53.5					

Field Work, 2024

Table 5 revealed a chi-square value of 367.776, with observed frequency of responses as VHE345, HE323, LE160 and VLE137 under the difference of 3 which also indicates the significant value of .000 and P. value of .000. Since this value is less than the alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis which states that Family instability has no significant influence on self-concept of secondary school students has been rejected. This implies that family instability have significant influence on self-concept of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State.

Hypothesis 3: Family instability has no significant influence on self-esteem of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State.

Table 6: Chi-Square Test for the influence of family instability on self-esteem of secondary school students

Reponses Mode	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df	Level Sign	Chi-Square	P.value	Decision
VHE	475	53.5	3	0.05	144.598	0.00	Sig.
HE	210	53.5					
LE	205	53.5					
VLE	180	53.5					

Field Work, 2024

This table indicates a chi-square value of 144.598, with observed frequency of responses as VHE475, HE210, LE205 and VLE180 under the difference of 3 which also revealed the significant value of .000 and P. value of .000. Since this value is less than the alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis which states that Family instability has no significant influence on self-esteem of secondary school students has been rejected. This implies that family instability have significant influence on self-esteem of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this study is organized around the research hypothesis. The three null hypotheses that were formulated and tested were all rejected.

The first hypothesis of the study revealed that family instability have significant influence on self-actualization of secondary school students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State. Respondents agreed that when there is conflict in their families it affects their efforts to achieve their ambitions in life. They often score lower in class because their parents will rather quarrel than assist them with their homework. Students also agreed that conflicts has made their parents to neglect their needs to achieve the type of career they desire for themselves. They strongly indicated that constant conflicts in their families is causing them to give up on their aspirations in life. This findings agrees with Fomby, and Cherlin, (2017) whose study revealed that family instability, as measured by changes in family structure (such as parental conflict, remarriage, or cohabitation), was associated with lower levels of children's self-esteem and achievement levels, life satisfaction, and academic achievement. It is also in line with Amato and

Anthony, (2014) who found that parental conflict was associated with lower levels of respondents' self-actualization and psychological well-being, but that the effect of conflict were stronger and more persistent over time. This findings explains why children raised from un-peaceful homes tend to achieve less in life.

The second hypothesis of the research revealed that family instability have significant influence on self-concept of students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State. Secondary school students' responses showed that they usually feel unlucky to be born in their families because of the constant conflict and lack of peace. They wish they were born in a families with absolute harmony. They also agreed that they feel neglected living in families with constant conflicts. They also feel worthless and homeless each time there is conflict in their families. This finding agrees with Johnson & Andrews (2017), whose research work found that family instability was significantly associated with lower levels of children's self-concept. Children who experienced more family transitions had lower scores on the Piers-Harris Children's Self-Concept Scale than children who experienced fewer family transitions. It also agrees with Chen and Lee (2015) who found that family instability was negatively associated with parental warmth and children's self-concept. Furthermore, parental warmth partially mediated the relationship between family instability and children's self-concept, suggesting that parental warmth can buffer the negative effects of family instability on children's self-concept. This explains why students from conflicts homes view themselves as less important among their peers.

The third hypothesis of the research revealed that family instability have significant influence on self-esteem of students in Konshisha local government area, Benue State. Students' responses indicated that they believe they can never be happy because their families are never peaceful. Students also agreed that they feel empty because they can't enjoy peace in their homes. They don't feel special like their friends who enjoy absolute harmony in their families. They also don't see themselves achieving anything good if the disunity in their families persist. It also shows that students feel depressed when there is a constant dispute in their families. This finding agrees with Sangi (2016) who found in his study that family instability had a significant negative impact on the self-esteem of children over time. Specifically, changes in family structure, parent-child conflict, and parental stress were all associated with lower self-esteem in children. It is also in line with the findings of Munchi (2015) which revealed that children from families experiencing instability had significantly lower self-esteem than children from stable families. Specifically, children from families experiencing parental conflict, parental conflict, and family relocation had lower self-esteem than children from stable families. These findings confirmed the observation that students from conflicting families often express some form of inferiority complex among their mates. They often see themselves as been less important.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the study concludes that; there is a significant influence of family instability on psychological adjustment of secondary school students in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the hypothesis of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should seek counselling as a professional ways of resolving conflicts rather than aggressive means which will affects their children psychological well-being.
2. Parents should always provide the warmth environment their children needs in order to develop a balanced self-concept, a good self-image for them to self-actualize their goals.
3. Teachers should also provide the basics guidance for students who are affected by family conflicts in order to enable them adjust better.

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